

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIALOGICAL SPEECH IN THE FRENCH LANGUAGE OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article provides detailed information about the educational technologies, methods and their importance used in the development of dialogic speech in French of general education students.*

Keywords: *dialogic speech, educational technologies, methods, speech pronunciation, speech competence.*

ТЕКСТ НАУЧНОЙ РАБОТЫ НА ТЕМУ «ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ ФРАНЦУЗСКОГО ЯЗЫКА УЧАЩИХСЯ ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ»

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена подробная информация об образовательных технологиях, методах и их значении, используемых в развитии диалогической речи на французском языке учащихся общеобразовательных школ.*

Ключевые слова: *диалогическая речь, образовательные технологии, методика, речевое произношение, речевая компетентность.*

INTRODUCTION

We know that one of the most important characteristics of a person is the ability to speak. Thought expressed through fluent speech is clear and pleasant. Speech acts are performed through a complex system of organs, in which the activity of the brain plays the main role, speech is a special and high-level form of communication unique to humans, in the process of speech communication, people exchange ideas and influence each other. Speech communication is carried out through language; language is a system of phonetic, lexical and grammatical tools, in order for human speech to be understandable and meaningful, the movements of speech organs must be clear and correct. In order to understand the movement of the speech pronunciation mechanism, it is necessary to have a good knowledge of the structure of the speech apparatus. Speech disorders are a field that has been studied for many years. Speech norms mean generally accepted variants of language use in the process of speech activity. The state of normal functioning of speech is determined by its deviation from language norms due to the weakening of psychophysiological mechanisms.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Primary school students learn a foreign language 2 hours a week, and during this lesson, students learn enough A2 level vocabulary for each topic based on the textbook. In primary grades, i.e. 1st graders, it is necessary to know at least 90-100 words. This indicator increases in the process of moving from class to class. It is known that there are approaches to determining the acquisition of foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities based on standards and criteria.

In the normative approach, the student's knowledge is evaluated on the basis of program requirements or in relation to the average indicator of the class. But when such an evaluation

method is used, the student's personal indicators are not taken into account. For example, a student who had a reading speed of 15 words per minute at the beginning of the quarter recorded a reading speed of 20 words per minute at the end of the quarter. Although his mastery rate has not reached the average level, it has increased to a certain extent. But a student with a reading speed of 20 words per minute at the beginning of the quarter showed a result of 22 words per minute at the end of the quarter. In this case, the first student increased by 5 (coefficient) steps, while the second student increased by 2 (coefficient) steps.

A student of junior high school age is very sensitive to grades and will take a reprimand like "you did it badly" as "you are bad". Therefore, the difference between the initial mastery index and the recorded result should be taken into account when evaluating students' knowledge. Even the smallest achievement of the student should be recognized in the form of "Bally, you are studying faster today than before", "You speak beautifully, I am happy about your success". Such an incentive inspires the student and increases his interest in the subject. Any teacher wants to know how well they are achieving their goals. As a result of teaching, what students will be able to say or write using the acquired language and speech material depends on the efforts of the teacher. For example, after the lessons related to the "Family" topic, students should be able to give brief oral or written information about their family (members). They should be able to give short answers to very simple questions about the age, profession, and interests of family members. Pupils are also required to memorize family riddles, quick recitations, poems and songs.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A modern teacher needs to determine these goals before starting each speech topic (Unit). A clear definition of the goal is an important basis for the adequate assessment of student performance. The teacher will be able to determine where there is a gap, which language material is difficult or easy to master, and whether linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences are acquired by each student in relation to the topic of speech. This information ensures high-quality and effective practical training. For example, a teacher acquires methodical competence in determining the amount of exercises for mastering language and speech material depending on its level of complexity, or determining the ration of exercises serving the acquisition of competencies based on their status as an educational goal or tool.

It is known that the main practical goal of teaching English in primary grades in accordance with the state education standard for foreign languages of the continuous education system and the English language curriculum for general secondary schools is communicative competence. is to ensure that it is taken at the initial A1 level. The practical goal is achieved through the acquisition of linguistic (speech and language), sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies. Linguistic competence according to DTS consists of speech competence (listening, speaking, reading and writing) and language competence (lexical, grammatical, phonetic competences and graphics and orthography). Based on this goal, the curriculum distinguishes two aspects of teaching content: what to teach (language material) and what to do (listening, speaking, reading and writing). That is, by learning and teaching language material (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation), the acquisition of communicative (information exchange) competence related to the skills and qualifications of speech activities is ensured.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that in speech development training, children's reading and telling stories is especially important. Teaching the retelling of works of art and staging them, memorizing poetry, imposes great skill and responsibility on the teacher. The more vividly the content of the work of art is expressed by the author, the more expressive and meaningful the speeches of the participants are, the more it excites children, the development of their feelings, the long memory of the events that happen to the heroes of the work, the vocabulary has a positive effect on the enrichment and grammatically correct formation of speech.

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